

1 **A primary cell culture model of HCV infection.**

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6 To study hepatitis C infection and life cycle in a cell culture model, we measured total transcription by
7 RNA-sequencing following infection of primary cells with HCV. Using this model, as a proof of concept we
8 demonstrate inhibition of *Arrdc4* by HCV.

9 Citations

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